

250 c.c. and a vigorous current of air was drawn through it, till the yellow precipitate of cobaltous phenylbiguanide, first formed, turned deep red in colour. Towards the latter part of the reaction, the flask was warmed on the water-bath when a pasty mass resulted. This was powdered in a mortar and washed with water till free from alkali. The precipitate was digested with absolute alcohol (75-100 c.c.) whereby a portion went into solution. With complete oxidation only a slight residue remains. The alcoholic solution was filtered and the filtrate, mixed with a little water, was kept overnight in the cold in a loosely corked conical flask. Red crystals, which separated, were filtered next morning. These were washed with alcohol and dried in vacuum over concentrated H_2SO_4 to a constant weight. The filtrate was preserved and used to extract the base in the next preparation, yield 2.3 g. A somewhat better yield was obtained by using caustic potash instead of caustic soda. {Found: N, 32.77, 32.98; Co, 9.25, 9.31. $[Co(PhBig)_2] \cdot 3H_2O$ requires N, 32.76; Co, 9.20 per cent} where $PhBigH = 1$ molecule of phenylbiguanide.

The substance forms rose-red crystals, insoluble in water and alcohol. It absorbs carbon dioxide from atmosphere. Boiling water and alkali have no action upon the substance, but concentrated acids decompose it. It liberates ammonia from ammonium salt solutions on boiling and melts with decomposition at about 200° .

Cobaltic trisphenylbiguanide dihydrate was prepared by adding an excess of caustic soda solution to that of the complex chloride (*vide infra*). The resulting precipitate was washed with water and dried as described above. {Found: N, 33.2; Co, 9.54. $[Co(PhBig)_3] \cdot 2H_2O$ requires N, 33.71; Co, 9.47 per cent}.

It forms pale rose crystals, insoluble in water but soluble in organic solvents, *e.g.*, ethyl alcohol, methyl alcohol, acetone etc., giving a deep red solution. It, therefore, differs from the trihydrate in this respect. Like the latter it melts with decomposition.

Cobaltic trisPhenylbiguanidine.—The above described hydrates, when heated in an air-oven to 145° - 150° for nearly 24 hours, lost their water. The anhydrous compounds on exposure to air, however, readily absorb water; these are pale rose crystals, soluble in alcohol.

From the trihydrate :—Loss of water = 7.15; (calc. = 8.52 per cent). {Found: Co, 10.07. $[Co(PhBig)_3]$ requires Co, 10.05 per cent}. The result for loss of water shows that the substance already lost a part of its water before drying in the oven.

From the dihydrate :—Loss of water = 5.97; (calc. = 5.78 per cent). {Found: Co, 9.97. $[Co(PhBig)_2]$ requires Co, 10.05 per cent}.

Cobaltic trisphenylbiguanidine, prepared by dehydration from the tri- or dihydrate, gave, in alcoholic solution by the ebullioscopic method, a molecular weight of 1000-1200, which is nearly twice its normal molecular weight (590). The dihydrate in the same solvent gave a molecular weight of about 1700 against its normal value of 626. This indicates polymerisation, due possibly to the formation of polynuclear complexes. Thus for the anhydrous compound it may be represented by the formula,

The higher value in the case of dihydrate may be attributed to a similar polymerisation involving three cobalt atoms.

Cobaltic trisphenylbiguanidinium chloride was prepared by treating the solid base in a mortar with cold dilute HCl till the mixture became slightly acid. A clear solution was first obtained from which, after a few minutes, the crystals of the complex chloride separated all at once. The chloride tends to separate as an oil unless the solution is cooled. The crystals were washed with cold water, dissolved in alcohol and reprecipitated by the addition of pure acetone. The product was washed with acetone and dried over concentrated H₂SO₄.

The substance forms needle-shaped orange crystals, soluble in water and alcohol, but insoluble in ether and acetone. {Found: N, 28.13; Cl, 14.40; Co, 7.98. [X]Cl₃ · 2.5 H₂O requires N, 28.32; Cl, 14.36; Co, 7.96 per cent} where X = [Co(PhBigH⁺)₃].

When heated to 110° for 15 hours the substance lost whole of its water and was converted into red anhydrous crystals.

Loss of weight = 6.04; Calc. water = 6.07 per cent.

Equivalent Conductivity at 35°.

<i>v</i> (dilution)	32	64	128	256	512	1024
λ_{∞} =	103.3	106.1	112.1	118.8	124.9	133.1
λ_{∞} =	141.3 (from Walden's formula).					

The valency of the complex ion from Ostwald-Bredig's rule = $\lambda_{1024} - \lambda_{32} = 133.1 - 103.3 = 2.98 \times 10$, i.e. 3.

Cryoscopic Measurement.

Subs. (g. /100 c.c. calc. anhydrous).	Depression. Δ	Mol. wt. m .	van't Hoff's factor. $i = M/m$.	Degree of dissociation. $\alpha = i - 1/n - 1$.
0.5342	0.045°	213.7	3.26	0.75

Where M = mol. wt. calculated (anhydrous), n = number of ions.

Magnetic Susceptibility at 30°.

Subs.	$\chi_m \times 10^6$	$\chi_M \times 10^6$
[X]Cl ₃ ·2.5H ₂ O	-0.5501	-408.0 (dia)

The solution of the complex chloride gave coloured precipitates with a number of complex anions, e.g. ferrocyanide, ferricyanide, nitroprusside, cobalticyanide, platinichloride, mercuri-iodide, bismuthi-iodide, thiosulphato-cobalticyanide, disulphito-cobalticyanide, chromithiocyanate and sodium phosphomolybdate.

Cobaltic tris-phenylbiguanidinium bromide was obtained as a red crystalline precipitate by adding a concentrated solution of potassium bromide to that of the complex chloride in the cold. The crystals were washed with water and dried over concentrated H₂SO₄. {Found : Br, 28.27; Co, 6.95. [X]Br₃·H₂O requires Br, 28.28; Co, 6.96 per cent}.

It is moderately soluble in water and in alcohol.

Cobaltic tris-phenylbiguanidinium iodide was prepared by double decomposition of the complex chloride and potassium iodide in the cold. The crystals, which separated, were washed with water whereby they changed into an oily mass. This was dissolved in alcohol and evaporated to dryness in vacuum over concentrated H₂SO₄, when a red glassy solid was obtained. {Found : I, 38.30; Co, 5.87. [X]I₃·H₂O requires I, 38.50; Co, 5.96 per cent}.

Cobaltic trisphenylbiguanidinium sulphate was prepared by digesting the complex base with a slight excess of dilute H₂SO₄ in a mortar and keeping the mixture overnight. The product was washed with water and dried in air. {Found : N, 25.62; S, 5.80; Co, 7.13. [X]₃(SO₄)₃·10H₂O requires N, 25.49; S, 5.82; Co, 7.16 per cent}.

The sulphate forms sparingly soluble red crystals.

Cobaltic trisphenylbiguanidinium nitrate was prepared by adding a concentrated solution of potassium nitrate to that of the complex chloride in the cold. The mixture, when cooled in ice, gave a crop of red crystals which were washed with cold water and dried over H₂SO₄. {Found : N, 32.80; Co, 7.53. [X](NO₃)₃· $\frac{1}{2}$ H₂O requires N, 32.10; Co, 7.52 per cent}.

Cobaltic trisphenylbiguanidinium nitrite was precipitated by adding a strong solution of potassium nitrite to that of the complex chloride in the cold. The crystals were washed and dried as described above. {Found : N (nitritic), 5'65 ; Co, 8'0. $[X](NO_2)_3 \cdot \frac{1}{2}H_2O$ requires N, (nitritic), 5'70 ; Co, 8'0 per cent}.

Cobaltic trisphenylbiguanidinium carbonate was prepared from a concentrated solution of sodium carbonate and that of the complex chloride in the cold. The crystals were washed and dried as in the previous case. {Found : C, 43'80; Co, 8'38. $[X]_2(CO_3)_3 \cdot 2H_2O$ requires C, 43'96; Co, 8'47 per cent}.

The substance forms pale rose crystals, moderately soluble in water and gives a solution strongly alkaline to litmus.

Cobaltic trisphenylbiguanidinium thiosulphate separated as rose-coloured crystals when a concentrated solution of sodium thiosulphate was added slowly to a solution of the complex chloride. These were washed and dried as above. {Found : N, 25'05; S, 11'78. Co, 7'18. $[X]_2(S_2O_3)_3 \cdot 7H_2O$ requires N, 25'66; S, 11'73; Co, 7'21 per cent.}

Cobaltic trisphenylbiguanidinium thiocyanate was precipitated by adding a strong solution of potassium thiocyanate to a concentrated solution of the complex chloride in the cold. When washed with cold water the crystals readily turned into an oily mass. This was dissolved in alcohol and the solution was evaporated to dryness in vacuum over H_2SO_4 . A red glassy mass was obtained. {Found : Co, 7'28; S, 11'78. $[X](SCN)_3 \cdot 3H_2O$ requires S, 11'72; Co, 7'21 per cent}.

Cobaltic trisphenylbiguanidinium dithionate was obtained as pale rose crystals by mixing together strong solutions of the complex chloride and sodium dithionate. {Found : S, 11'24; Co, 6'99. $[X]_2(S_2O_8)_3 \cdot 2H_2O$ requires S, 11'32; Co, 6'97 per cent}.

Cobaltic trisphenylbiguanidinium chromate was precipitated in the form of pale rose crystals when a solution of sodium chromate was added to that of the complex chloride. {Found : Co, 7'55; Cr, 10'16. $[X]_2(CrO_4)_3 \cdot 2H_2O$ requires Co, 7'54 ; Cr, 9'97 per cent}.